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THINKING WITH CARE - GENDER, DIVERSITY AND ENVIRONMENTAL RESPONSIBILITY IN ENGINEERING EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

The paper presents an ongoing study of the one-semester compulsive module Blue Engineering at Technical University Berlin (TU Berlin), which is designed to raise social and environmental awareness and responsibility of engineering students. Homepage research, ethnographic observation and a qualitative analysis of 17 learning journals written by students of the module are used to explore (1) how the gender and diversity unit was perceived by students and (2) if being taught social and environmental responsibility helped engineering students to develop a caring attitude towards marginalised human and more-than-humans.

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Gender in the engineering classroom

Gender plays a central role in engineering. As an essential dimension it structures the field of students, researchers and employees in engineering subjects such as civil engineering, electrical engineering and information technology as well as computer science. The figures for new students show for Germany that while in 2018 51.3% of students that started to study were women* [1] only 26,3% of women* were among new students in the first semester of an engineering degree [2]. Various studies show that the under-representation of women in engineering contributes to a discriminatory professional culture which leads to high drop-outs, worse working contracts and early career endings for women in technology driven subjects [3].

1.2 Gender and Diversity Skills as Key Qualifications in a Changing World

Processes of technology development and technology design are deeply gendered. Therefore a fundamental change in the professional culture is needed in order to eliminate discrimination and marginalisation due to gender and other social inequality categories [4]. Even though the implementation of gender and diversity issues within engineering education is still in the beginning [5], social and environmental responsibility of engineers are coming already into focus due to fast technological and ecological changes of our world. Diversity and inclusivity are becoming increasingly important for engineering sciences due to the fact that technical artifacts more and more are required to be planned with regard to the resources needed, applicability, climate justice and social justice. Also large international organisations like the American Society for Engineering Education (ASEE) and the European Society for

Engineering Education (SEFI) claim that gender and diversity issues need to be reflected in engineering practices and curricula [6].

1.3. Posthumanist Caring as a Responsible Attitude Towards the World

Working towards diversity, equity and inclusion has a long history in feminism. In its academic forms such as women and gender studies, teaching gender has also been in a way to teach – figuratively spoken – to care for marginalised others. Feminist researchers in science and technology claim that it is important to reflect gender and diversity not only in the classroom but as entangled with processes of science and technology making[7]. New materialism and the posthumanist approach point out the significance of matter and humans entanglement with more-than-humans such as animals, plants or technical artifacts. Thinking with care is in the following understood with María Puig de la Bellacasa as an engagement with a responsible attitude towards the world. In her speculative exploration of care Bellacasa develops a feminist and posthumanist understanding which takes into account „that in times binding technosciences with naturecultures, the livelihoods and fates of so many kinds and entities on this planet are unavoidably entangled“ [8]. To respect that entanglement of human and more-than-humans can be seen as a basic condition for responsible engineering in a changing world.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 *Blue Engineering* as a Way of Teaching Care

In the following, brief insights into Technical University Berlins' module *Blue Engineering* are given. Since 2011 *Blue Engineering* is located at the Department of Engineering of Machine Systems. It is offered as a 6-ECTS compulsory elective module in the courses mechanical engineering, information technology in mechanical engineering, transport, sustainable management and industrial engineering. The module's central objective is to raise students' awareness of their social *and* environmental responsibility. On average, 80 students attend the four-hour module every semester that entails a range of units on social and environmental issues such as the critical encounter of the idea as technology as problem-solving, productionist worldview or the paradigm of constant growing. Regularly a unit on gender and diversity-issues is offered which consists on talk of a gender expert, an introduction on gender-sensitive language, a game that helps students to reflect on diverse positioning in society and a final discussion. Module's assessment takes the form of a portfolio examination and, in addition to an implementation and development of a *Blue Engineering* learning unit, requires the submission of a learning journal, which the students conduct over the entire teaching period. The keeping of a learning journal is understood as an important part of the individual learning process and is seen as having an enormous impact on students capability to reflect on the complex topics. Therefore students are asked to deliberate every learning-unit while answering questions that are given to them to stimulate a reflection on the given issue and their connection to the field of engineering. Also, they are allowed to experiment in a creative way with the aesthetic form of their reflection [9].

2.2 Research Design

An exploratory study of *Blue Engineering* has been carried out by the author through homepage research, ethnographic observation and an analysis of 26 learning journals of one cohort of students taking part in 2018/2019. Homepage research aimed to get more general information on how the module is structured and what the instruction were to write the learning journals. Ethnographic observation and a content analysis [10] of the learning journals were conducted to get insights into (1) how the gender and diversity unit was perceived by students and (2) if being taught of social and environmental responsibility helped engineering students to engage with a caring attitude.¹ The learning journals were used in this study to gain an overall impression of students' perception of gender and diversity issues and to get insights into their individual thoughts and reflections since educational research shows that learning journals foster skills such as the personal and critical reflection and are therefore useful for promoting metacognitive skills like creativity and originality [11]. Therefore the learning journals were analysed with respect to the following main themes (1) acceptance of the gender and diversity-unit (Was the gender and diversity unit seen as important/interesting? How did students reflect on the content of the gender & diversity unit?), (2) and thinking with care (Did students engage with care as an attitude towards human and more-than—humans? Did students link gender and diversity issues to issues of environmental responsibility?).

2.2 Results

2.2.1 Perception of the gender and diversity-unit

An initial analysis made it clear that not all of the 26 learning journals that were released for research purposes included reflexive content on the gender and diversity unit. Nine learning journals either did not contain an entry for the gender and diversity-unit, or they only included a collection of quotes or images on the subject. The remaining 17 learning journals were written by seven women* and ten men*. They showed that all students found it in general appropriate that a teaching unit on gender and diversity was part of the *Blue Engineering* module. Eleven students, almost two thirds (64.7%), expressed explicitly their strong agreement on issues related to gender, equality and diversity and considered information on these issues to be important in their education in their learning journals. Nevertheless, there were also some varieties in the grade of acceptance and engagement with gender and diversity in the learning journals. Also, the study revealed that students were strongly affected by issues around gender and diversity. Language turned out to be quite emotional. There were students who passionately expressed their gratitude over a gender and diversity unit in their engineering education. It was striking that students seemed to have more trouble to integrate gender and diversity issues into their mindsets than environmental issues. For example some students expressed that they found gender and diversity issues very important while simultaneously showed reluctance to the gender and diversity unit. For instance, one student considered the presentation of the topic too superficial and preferred instead to deepen his/her* knowledge of the relationship between technology and gender & diversity. Another student accepted that a change in language practices had to be carried out with regard to the representation of different

¹ Learning journals were handed in for research on a voluntary basis.

genders, but also was hesitating to do so by him/herselves*. For example, the student was worried that it could be too complicated to use gender-sensitive language or that by representing several genders in language, hegemonic gender roles would be re-established. The student wrote: “Isn’t it (gender sensitive language, *sd*) the absolute opposite of the goal (to speak gender-sensitive, *sd*) if I have to identify to certain categories again?” (learning journal 5, translation *sd*).

2.2.3 Engaging with Care

Being taught of social and environmental responsibility helped engineering students clearly to focus on different aspects of gender, diversity and environmental responsibility. Learning journals exhibited students’ engagement with a caring attitude towards human and more-than-humans. For instance, all 26 students showed signs of unsettlement when reflecting on the amount of energy they consumed or their difficulties to avoid plastic. Also, all students claimed in their learning journals in different ways that technology should be used as an opportunity to enhance the world in a more fair and sustainable way and that caring for the world must be the primacy in the development of technology. Several students expressed their gratitude for the *Blue Engineering* module. One student wrote for instance: “I am very happy, that there is such a module that reflect on the need for social aspects of engineering” (learning journal 14, translation *sd*). However, analysis also made visible that students did not link gender and diversity issues to issues of environmental responsibility. Rather, students recognised gender and diversity issues as additive to environmental responsibilities.

3 SUMMARY AND ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

In sum, results indicate that *Blue Engineerings’* goal, the development of engineers’ social and environmental responsibility, works successfully as an epistemic umbrella that enables students to reorder their knowledge towards gender, diversity and sustainability goals. Learning journals showed that students are motivated to critically engage with a caring attitude towards human and more-than-humans and that they appear to be willing to take over social and environmental responsibility. Findings also point out that while students were in general very interested in the gender and diversity unit their understanding of the issue can still be improved. To make students better understand their key-role as agents of social and environmental justice it would maybe be helpful to teach gender and diversity issues more closely to the overlying epistemic umbrella of social and environmental responsibility possibly intertwined with care toward marginalised humans and more-than human. Also, findings give indications that students possibly would profit from more time to debate and reflect on gender and diversity issues. Entangled with that, learning journals made it visible that it could also be supportive to relate the gender and diversity unit to research of feminist science and technology studies to give students more insights into the close relationship between gender, diversity and technology on a scientific level [12]. The author would like to acknowledge the support of *Blue Engineerings’* staff and students in the production of this work.

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